

Rethinking the use of antimicrobials in livestock production systems

Policy Brief nº 6

How to meet the public health challenge of antibiotic resistance in a context of rapid intensification of poultry production?

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This policy brief contributes to the main goal of the ROADMAP project which is to analyse the practices and decision systems of farmers, veterinarians and other professionals involved in managing the health of farmed animals, and to the specific objective of identifying levers/incentives for a more prudent use of antibiotics in livestock production

Mozambique is experiencing a strong growth of its poultry production, allowing a substantial decrease of importations. At the same time, the number of stakeholders in the veterinary drugs markets, and the consumption of antibiotics in poultry farming skyrocketed, with potential risks of antimicrobial resistance in humans, animals and the environment. The challenge for the Mozambican Government is to support the development of the national poultry value chain without compromising the public health.

This document should be of particular relevant for Mozambican authorities with interest on animal health and production, as well as farmers and other livestock professionals, from Mozambique and other Low and Middle income Countries (LMIC).

OVERVIEW

Like many other African countries, Mozambique is experiencing a strong growth of poultry production (it doubled during the last 5 years) and consumption (from 3.3 kg/cap/year in 2015, to 4.3 in 2021), with an increasing number of new and little experienced farmers entering into the commercial poultry sector. At the same time, the number of economic stakeholders on the veterinary drugs markets, as well as the diversity of vet drugs available on the market skyrocketed.

Sources : based on data from MADER, MEF-IGC

The challenge for the Mozambican Government is to support and regulate these rapid economic and technical changes, despite low resources, in particular related to limited number of livestock extensionists, and regulatory instruments on vet drugs trade and prescription. The activities conducted in the ROADMAP project Case Study (CS) in Mozambique, in partnership with the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MADER, National Directorate of Livestock) and the Association of Poultry Producers of Maputo Province (ADAM), highlighted the functioning of the vet drugs market, the use of antibiotics (AB) by poultry producers, and the involvement of veterinary professionals in the management of AMR risk.

RELATED PROJECT OUTPUTS

- Machavane C., Manhiça, A. Macuamule C. (2023). **Estudo transversal do uso de antimicrobianos na produção de frangos na província e cidade de Maputo. ROADMAP Project Report.**
- Figuié M. (2023). **Findings of an on-line survey on veterinary practices and AMU in livestock farming in Mozambique. ROADMAP Project Report.**
- Cuinanhe C. et al. (2023). **Avaliação qualitativa do uso de AB na produção avícola na Cidade e Província de Maputo. ROADMAP Project Report.**
- Sandulane V., Maunela, P., Macuamule C. (2022) **Importation of veterinary drugs in Mozambique during the period 2018-2020. ROADMAP Project Report and Practical Abstract.**
- Cuinhane C. et al. (2023). **A multi-stakeholder initiative for a more prudent use of antibiotics in the Poultry Sector in Mozambique. ROADMAP Technical leaflet**
- Figuié M. et al. (2022). **Barreiras e condutores para uma utilização prudente de antibióticos no sector avícola moçambicano. ROADMAP Practical Abstract**
- **Electronic Data base** on Importation of veterinary drugs in Mozambique 2018-2022.

AMR risk management as a multilevel and multisectoral policy

- 1. There is a good translation of international recommendations into national policies, but there is still limited transition into local levels.
- 2. The problem of AMR is framed as a One Health (OH) and inter-ministerial issue (handle mainly by MADER and the Ministry of Health). Within MADER the issue is specifically dealt with as a health challenge, with little consideration on the related agricultural development issue.

Farmers' use of AB

- 3. Broiler production in Mozambique is essentially based on a single model of production system (Ross or Cob, raised in 30 days).
- 4. Most poultry farmers do not have vocational training in poultry farming, and the existing livestock schools do not offer short-term training courses.
- 5. Poultry farming is developed under inadequate biosecurity conditions including poor hygiene due to lack of economic capacity to invest in modern poultry houses adapted to extreme adverse climatic conditions. AB used as a quick fix.
- 6. Current poultry farming system is heavily dependent on AB use to counteract the low quality of feed, chicks and the stressful environment (presence of pests, high microbial contamination, extreme heat, quality of water, etc.).

(1) Engagement of provincial and district authorities in AMR governance and adjustment of national policies to different local contexts.

(2 and 3) An agroecological transition in poultry farming should consider diversification of production systems, adapted to the diversity of farming contexts, and be less dependent on AB use for economic profitability.

(4) Encourage the establishment of short-term (3-6 months) vocational training centres on poultry farming and promote short-term training on appropriate poultry farming for farmers and/or other people interested in starting poultry farming as well as other stakeholders in the sector.

(5) Promote initiatives to support poultry farming and social investment based on revolving and interest-free credit for women and young farmers, as well as access to technical support by qualified professionals for the responsible use of antibiotics.

(6) Establish quality control mechanisms for feed, chicks and veterinary drugs.

(6) Urban planning for a coordinated implementation of cooperatives and access to clean water.

RESULTS

7. The use of AB is further aggravated as a result of frequent disruptions in the broiler market chain, including inconsistent high and low demand periods, poor slaughtering and storage infrastructures.
8. Poultry farmers' reliance on nonqualified sellers of veterinary drugs.

Drugs access and regulation

9. Expanding and poorly regulated vet drugs market
10. The risk of AMR is an opportunity seized by MADER to update the regulatory framework on veterinary drugs and animal health.
11. In certain geographical locations, common informal markets are the only places from where poultry farmers can access to veterinary drugs.
12. The Government of Mozambique has promulgated legislation (Decreto nº. 26/2009: Regulamento de Sanidade Animal), prohibiting the use of hormones and growth promoters. But some AB classified by the European Medicine Agency (EMA) as A (to avoid) or B (to restrict) are still imported in Mozambique for animal use (E.g. fosfomicin, colistin, cefquinome sulphate, enrofloxacin, neomycin and kanamycin sulphate), including as growth promoters.
13. Many stakeholders know veterinary medicines by their commercial names without knowledge on the active ingredients.

RECOMMENDATIONS

(7) Increase the slaughtering and meat storage capacity, through establishment of small scale units in within major and minor markets.

(8, 9) Reinforcing control measures on the qualification of vet drugs sellers.

(9, 10, 11) Regulation of the veterinary drugs market is much-needed. However, this should not hamper farmers' access to veterinary medicines and other inputs.

(12) Extend regulation aiming at rational use of AB and largely communicate on the regulation and its updates.

(13, 14) Facilitate access to information on the composition and use of vet drugs (e.g. mandatory presence of package leaflet in Portuguese).

The ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 817626.

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RESULTS

Technical assistance

14. Veterinarians are aware of the risk of AMR and ask for clear guidance's on AB use. Communication is very global ("use AB rationally"). There is need for more specific and practical communication with professionals.

15. Animal health professionals have limited access, if any, to alternatives to AB and tools for improved diagnostics and prescription.

RECOMMENDATIONS

(11-14) Prepare, disseminate and use more specific and detailed guidelines for AB use ("to avoid", "to reserve" etc.)

(15) Improve access to AB alternatives (e.g. probiotics, prebiotics, vaccines, etc.) as well as antimicrobial susceptibility testing facilities and facilitation of continued research on local non AB solutions.

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